

**GENERAL METHODOLOGICAL PRINCIPLES OF DEVELOPMENTAL
EDUCATION IN THE TRAINING OF FUTURE PHYSICIANS****Abdujalilova Nafisaxon Abduvaliyevna**

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Abstract. In the article, developmental education is one of the important directions in teaching theory and practice. Developmental education means organizing education in such a way that the content of the process, their teaching methods and forms are aimed at the comprehensive development of future doctors, and the practical application of the knowledge gained.

Key words: Developmental education, teaching process, methods, therapist, metasubject competencies.

Annotasiya. Maqolada rivojlantiruvchi ta'limni o'qitish nazariyasi va amaliyotidagi muhim yo'nalishlardan biri hisoblanadi. Rivojlantiruvchi ta'lim deyilganida o'qitishni shunday tarzda tashkil etish tushuniladiki, bunda o'quv jarayoni mazmuni, o'qitish metod va shakllari bo'lajak shifokorlarni har tomonlama rivojlantirishga, ularni nazariy olgan bilimlarini amalda qo'llashga yo'naltirib o'qitiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Rivojlantiruvchi ta'lim, o'qitish jarayoni, metodlar, shifokor, metapredmet kompetensiyalar.

Аннотация: В статье развивающее обучение является одним из важных направлений в теории и практике обучения. Развивающее образование Подразумевается, что обучение организуется таким образом, чтобы содержание учебного процесса, методы и формы обучения были направлены на всестороннее развитие будущих врачей и практической применение полученных ими теоретический знаний.

Ключевые слова: развивающее обучение, учебный процесс, методика, терапевт, метапредметные компетенции

Introduction. In accordance with the Presidential Decree on the implementation of the State Program within the framework of the “Year of Science, Enlightenment, and Digital Economy Development,” adopted as part of the Strategy of Actions for the Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017–2021, the development of a Concept for advancing science, including medicine, until 2030 was identified as a priority task. This decree is of particular importance as it aims to ensure the rapid development of medical sectors and disciplines, mobilize intellectual and financial resources, establish new areas in medicine, further enhance existing branches, and effectively utilize scientific and innovative potential. In the long term, it focuses on defining priority directions for the continuous reform of medical science, training highly qualified specialists with modern knowledge and independent thinking, and elevating the

modernization of scientific infrastructure to a new qualitative level. These urgent tasks highlight the necessity of creating a developmental educational environment within the higher education system. In response to these demands, new higher educational institutions that meet contemporary theoretical and practical requirements are being established. In particular, the Central Asian Medical University was founded in the city of Fergana under the leadership of Nurullo Shukurullayevich. Since October 3, 2022, the university has begun admitting students on a competitive basis in the fields of General Medicine, Pediatrics, and Dentistry, providing them with high-quality education delivered by experienced and qualified faculty members. Developmental education represents one of the key directions in modern pedagogical theory and practice. It refers to the organization of the educational process in such a way that its content, teaching methods, and forms are aimed at the comprehensive development of future physicians. It is important to emphasize the distinguishing features of developmental education. Like traditional informational-reproductive education, it fulfills three main pedagogical tasks: teaching (knowledge acquisition), development, and upbringing. However, unlike the informational-reproductive approach, which relies heavily on memorization and passive absorption of ready-made knowledge, developmental education emphasizes active understanding and application. To reinforce theoretical knowledge and facilitate its practical application, clinical training sessions have been organized at the “MERIDIAN” clinic both during and outside classroom hours. Under the guidance of experienced medical professionals, students acquire essential practical skills and competencies. As noted by I.P. Pavlov, despite the significant role of clinical practice in understanding disease pathology and morphology throughout history, a complete analysis of disease mechanisms can only be achieved through experimental methods. The advantage of experimentation lies in the controlled conditions and clearly defined influencing factors, which explains its fundamental role in medical science. Within developmental education:

a) The instructional function goes beyond rote memorization and involves mastering theoretical concepts such as laws, principles, models, diagrams, and tables, while also fostering metadisciplinary competencies;

b) The developmental function prioritizes professional orientation at all stages of learning, encouraging mastery of scientific and creative methods;

c) The educational function aims to develop the ability of future physicians to independently apply theoretical knowledge in practice, requiring consistent interaction and collaboration between teacher and student. The structure of developmental education involves progressively complex interdisciplinary tasks that not only stimulate the acquisition of new knowledge and skills but also encourage the creation of new problem-solving approaches and methods. This process activates previously acquired knowledge while promoting hypothesis generation, disease investigation, and the development of treatment methods. As a result, students enhance their intellectual abilities, personal qualities, and metadisciplinary competencies. In this context, the teacher’s primary role is to organize learning activities that foster independent thinking and competency development. Developmental education engages students in diverse activities aimed at improving creativity, critical thinking, memory, communication skills, motivation, and professional competence. By involving students in active learning processes, educators contribute to the continuous improvement of their knowledge and skills. A key aspect of developmental education is the enhancement of students’ cognitive activity. Future physicians not only acquire knowledge and skills but also learn to diagnose and treat patients effectively. This requires continuous intellectual growth and professional development. Therefore,

educators must be able to assess the developmental level of students and set clear learning objectives that encourage independent knowledge acquisition. When students are motivated to solve real clinical problems, they engage in observation, analysis of symptoms, and application of various treatment methods. This process fosters deep and critical thinking. Thus, the developmental function of education is realized through such activities. Both education and upbringing contribute to the holistic development of the future specialist's personality. Although it may seem unnecessary to emphasize the developmental function separately, practical experience shows that it can and should be implemented systematically. This approach involves engaging students in activities that develop sensory perception, motor skills, intellectual capacity, emotional stability, motivation, and professional competence. The concept of "developmental education" emerged in pedagogy in the 1960s and has since emphasized not only the acquisition of knowledge and specialized skills but also the overall development of the learner through targeted pedagogical strategies.

Conclusion. The progress of society necessitates fundamentally new approaches to developing the personality, metadisciplinary competencies, creativity, and ethical potential of future physicians. This, in turn, requires identifying перспективные directions in medical education and designing innovative strategies for its further advancement.

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